

THE CONCEPT OF PINK MARKETING: A META-ANALYSIS FROM THE GENDER DIFFERENCES PRESPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

Women are half the society, but so far women's issues have not been given proper attention in marketing researches. The world needs review papers cover furtherly the nature of dealing with women, with full respect for their rights, without being considered them as second-class populations on this planet. Thousands of scientific studies have identified dozens of gender differences between males and females in most physical, medical and behavioral fields. But literature needs researches that combine these gender differences in order to achieve effective integrations between men and women rather than racial discrimination against women. 17 meta-analyses papers were included in this current study; the results identified more than 74 fundamental differences that must be observed when dealing with women to achieve effective communication. The depended meta-analyses studies covered 1863 of previous studies; their samples were collected from more than 58 countries. One of the seventeen meta-analyses studies was added by this present study, it includes 65 of previous studies. The essence of the modern concept of marketing can be expressed in the question: "How (you/and what you offer) to be accepted from others?" therefore, this study presents a significant contribution in this context by suggesting the academic proposal of the "Marketing Pink" concept. It also could be considered as a strong review paper on the context of how to achieve more effective communication between women and men. Future researchers can address the components of the pink marketing mix and analyze other areas of gender differences to support the issues of successful dealing with women.

KEYWORDS: *Meta-Analysis, Review Paper, Pink Marketing, Gender Differences, Women Studies, Communication Skills, Negotiation, Persuasion*

Research Type: Review Paper.

1. INTRODUCTION

A set of researchers may avoid researching on gender differences issues, fearing that they may be accused of racial discrimination. Literary studies are in dire need of such research, in order to achieve more effective communication among the members of society, not for the purpose of gender discrimination. The qualitative differences can be divided into a range of categories: physical, social, behavioral and many other sides. The modern concept of contemporary marketing is no longer limited to the marketing of goods and services to profit organizations only, but extends to include the marketing of all values, and to serve all individuals, governmental institutions or non-profit organizations. From this

perspective, dozens of gender differences that have been proven through many scientific studies must be applied in the field of contemporary marketing. It must be said that marketing for women is no longer acceptable to the perspective of men alone by ignoring all those differences among males and females. This study launches the concept of pink marketing which confirms how to market to women? and how women market to others? Finally, this study aims to answer the following four questions:

- Q1: Who did use the term pink marketing for the first time? And when?
- Q2: What is the suitable definition of pink marketing?
- Q3: What are the main aspects of gender differences from the marketing perspective?

Q4: What is the proposed framework of pink marketing, as a separated branch of marketing science?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section includes five sub-sections to discuss the main factors according to the previous studies perspectives. The gab of each group of studies be presented on the end of discussing separately to explain what literature in-need to. The fifth sub-section is to shed light on the expected contributions of current study.

2.1. Gender Differences Studies

The analysis of gender differences is a common factor in marketing studies [45]. Previous studies confirmed a large set of significant gender differences; attitudes [86], [82], values [55], communication languages [15], psychological perspectives, behaviors of information search [64], consumption [50], or perceptions/evaluations of products [31], [81], [9]. Among the large scale of present meta-analysis, there were more than 12 thousand of articles included the phrase of Gender Differences in their titles. They covered various and variety areas of research. However, a lot of other researches which discuss gender differences, may not include the same phrase in their titles. Previous studies of gender differences may be categorized from three main aspects. First, according to the number of gender differences included in each study. Most of them focused on a specific different as a variable of research, in each study. Second, according to the number of countries in which the study was applied. Most of the previous studies were applied on just one country in each study. Third, according to the research tool. Studies have often used questionnaires or experiments. minority of previous studies which depend on the method of meta-analysis, because it may need large and special efforts of research. Meta-analysis studies support us with the significant contributions of previous studies through comparative analysis. Furthermore, previous studies may be categorized from many other aspects (e.g. subjects, results or date of publication). Future researchers should to give more attention for this methodology of research to enrich the scientific theories.

2.2. The Modern Concept of Marketing

The concept of marketing emerged at the beginning of 20th century, as a function of distribution for goods [4]. Subsequently, this traditional concept was developed through several stages [78], [59], [79]. Sub-functions of marketing were limited, consisting of distribution, selling and advertising activities [57]. Furthermore, traditional concept of marketing was directed only for profit-organizations. However, the modern concept of marketing has become much extensive than before. Until ^{May}2017, the adopted definition of marketing by the American Marketing Association board of directors is "The activity, set of institutions, and processes for creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large" (Approved in ^{July}2013, <https://www.ama.org>). This definition is still working as the most common cited definition among marketing authors, it refers to three contemporary aspects [4]. First, the product concept was evolved to include even individuals, countries, ideas and anything presenting to others, not only goods and services [63]. Second, the importance of marketing has become required clearly for any type of organizations; governmental, international, non-profit or any of the other types, not only for profit organizations [35]. Third, the current target audience of marketing activities was expanded to include beneficiaries, stakeholders, employees and anyone deals with the marketers, not only traditional customers. In other words, the main core of the modern concept of marketing is how to make people accept you and your offer? or how to deal with others? Therefore, the applications of marketing were expanded to cover every side of the life. Now, it is common to find studies in marketing applied to multi areas including business [11], non-profit activities, politics [63], religion [35] and all other fields. The recent concept of modern marketing can be briefly expressed as "acceptance gaining". It is no longer just a business but has become closer to the concept of effective communication.

Marketing literature in need to special efforts of research from the macro level, to update the marketing thought.

2.3. Marketing to/by Women

Women represent half of the world's population. Directly or indirectly; women

account for about 85% of overall consumer spending, including autos to healthcare [66], [6]. Women are main players in economics, marketing and any activity of the life [78]. Females not only act as customers, but also, they are working as effective actors [59]. On the macro level of marketing, researchers should to think about what does that mean? Marketing literature is in real need to answer two main questions about this issue; first, to what extent males and females are different from marketing perspective? Second, is the marketing theory being in need to a specific branch focusing on: how to market to/by women? Modern concept of marketing is wider than just selling or transferring the ownership of goods [4]. Therefore, marketing should to include an essential specialty covering how to deal with women? and how the marketing by women? Furthermore, marketing to/by women not means just profit transactions, but it contains all communications even nonprofit transactions [66]. Women act multi roles in market transactions; customer, marketer, direct/indirect influencer on marketing decisions.

Therefore, from the academic and applied perspectives, the point of view about the gender factor must be changed and updated in future researches.

2.4. Why Pink as a Symbol?

Marketing to women is known informally as "Pink Marketing" [87]. No specific definition for pink marketing was found through the wide literature of this current study. A set of authors talked about pink marketing as marketing to women only [6], [38]. Present study defines pink marketing as "The marketing to/by women". According to the modern concept of marketing, pink marketing should to include the dealing with women in general, whether they are marketers or customers. Marketing researchers may avoid going into this topic for fear of describing their studies with discrimination. A lot of studies discussed the impact of colors on individuals from the psychological perspectives. Pink is the most common color to symbolize women in formal uses which have high importance (e.g. breast cancer) [30]. Furthermore, pink color was associated with women to the extent that women prefer it even with harmful products (e.g. cigarette packaging) [19]. Pink color is described as a global language to attract women through the suggested term of

"Pink Globalization" [87]. No one can assert exactly who suggested the term of pink marketing for the first time? or when? But one of the most important events on this context is the first round of the conference of Marketing to Women MTW, in 2003. This conference has become annually so far, since that date.

On the same context, a little group of researchers presented early attempts to understand the marketing to women (e.g. [23], [6], [38], [56]).

2.5. Expected Contributions of Present Study

Although the large set of studies which confirm the gender differences, but researchers usually satisfy with these results without thinking about marketing to/by women as a new specific specialty of marketing. In other words, are the marketing tools suitable for both women and men in the same way? present study aims to answer this question under the title of pink marketing term through two large scale of meta-analysis. The expected contributions of this meta-analysis are as follows:

- Present a comprehensive meta-analysis including a large set of gender differences depending on previous studies, from marketing perspective.
- Adopt the term of Pink Marketing as a scientific term in marketing researches and literatures.
- Highlight the idea of creating a new specialty of marketing focusing on how to market to/by women?
- Support academics and practitioners who are interested in effective communications from the modern concept of marketing perspective.

The only research hypothesis of this study can be expressed as follows:

H: There are Variety and various of significant gender differences require a specific term covering the marketing to/by women.

3. METHODOLOGY

This method section explains the way of collecting data and how the analysis of this data. This section includes three main sub-sections covering the literature search, inclusion/exclusion criteria and comprehensive survey. Current study depends on the e-system of

the best ranked scientific database. All the steps followed in this study were based on objective criteria without any prejudice or personal intervention from the author. The recent study included all the references of the database between 1990 up to ^{May}2017, and the inclusion/exclusion processes depended on limited terms and the classification of the database e-system.

3.1. literature Search

A large computerized source of scholarly literature was used in present study. This source is *Web of Science WOS* database. Until the end of ^{May}2017, *WOS* database included 77,339,971 references on two categories. First, *Web of Science Core Collection WOSCC*, which collects the following six cited indexes; *Science Citation Index Expanded SCI-EXPANDED* (1900-^{May}2017), *Social Sciences Citation Index SSCI* (1900-^{May}2017), *Arts & Humanities Citation Index A&HCI* (1975-^{May}2017), *Conference Proceedings Citation Index- Science CPCI-S* (1990-^{May}2017), *Conference Proceedings Citation Index- Social Science & Humanities CPCI-SSH* (1990-^{May}2017), *Emerging Sources Citation Index ESCI* (2015-^{May}2017). Until the end of ^{May}2017, *WOSCC* included 64,639,971 cited references, and it was used for obtaining the results of the two meta-analysis of present study. Second, six other large databases including; *Current Contents Connect* (1998-^{May}2017), *Derwent Innovations IndexSM* (1963-^{May}2017), *KCI-Korean Journal Database* (1980-^{May}2017), *MEDLINE* (1950-^{May}2017), *Russian Science Citation Index* (2005-^{May}2017), *SciELO Citation Index* (1997-^{May}2017). These six databases included 12,699,845 references until the end of ^{May}2017. This group of databases was added to *WOSCC* database during the search about using the specific phrase "Pink Marketing" among all the seven databases of *WOS*.

3.2. Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

A strategy of no-personal-selection by author was followed in this meta-analysis. Any study to be included in the meta-analysis (1) or (2), a set of criteria had to be met as the following: first, only English articles were included. Second, research area had to be related to the meta-analysis core. According to *WOS* categories, there were five related areas of research, as follows: business economics, social sciences, women' studies, public administration, social issues and communication. Other research

areas were excluded (e.g. biomedicine, biomedical sciences, cell Biology and engineering). Third, different keywords were used for each one of the two meta-analysis. The phrases of Meta-analysis and Gender Difference had to be addressed in the title of any study to be included to meta-analysis (1). The keywords used in meta-analysis (2) were Gender Differences in the title item, and Marketing in the topic item of the survey. This study included all the articles which met the inclusion criteria, of *WOSCC* database, without sampling or personal selection by author. Furthermore, no time limitations for the included studies, because the two meta-analysis covered all the available cited references of the source from 1900-^{May}2017. These criteria were followed to avoid bias as much as possible.

3.3. Comprehensive Survey

A comprehensive survey was followed by this study, without any limitations about the date of publish. All included studies were selected according to the inclusion criteria. Sampling was not used in this study; therefore, additional statistical analysis is not required. Present meta-analysis depended on the results of the included studies, which used a group of statistical analysis to confirm their implications. This meta-analysis included two studies. First study included previous meta-analysis studies. Second one included previous non-meta-analysis studies. Only significant results of previous studies, which were confirmed in this study.

4. RESULTS

This section answers of the study questions and presents the judgment of the research hypothesis. Results section included three main sub-sections covering overall results, results of study 1, results of study 2, groups of gender differences and the result of the research hypothesis.

4.1. Overall Results

Fig.1 shows the diagram of inclusion/exclusion of previous meta-analysis studies. According to the inclusion criteria, 274 articles were chosen among more than 64 million references of *WOSCC* database. Then, 193 studies were excluded due to various reasons. Most excluded cases were done for the studies which had not met the core of present study, more than 106 of them discuss the discrimination

of labor market. The other 87 articles are not related to the main topic of the study completely (e.g. the studies of medicine effects). Finally, only 81 studies fit the criteria of the present study, included 65 non-meta-analyses and 16 meta-analysis covered 1798 studies. Total number of the included studies is 1863 studies (=1798+65). Compared with other studies, this number is a large scale exceeded any of other previous meta-analysis study. The modern

concept of marketing (which was introduced through section 1.2. of present study) should to be understood clearly before presenting the results of two meta-analyses, because some factors may be appearing unusual (e.g. cheating or advantage in school). From the modern concept of marketing, pink marketing term refers to the large concept of dealing with women, not how to sell something to them?

Fig.1 Diagram of the search strategies and inclusion process. WOSCC=Web Of Science Core Collection

4.2. Results of Study 1

Study 1 presents a meta-analysis included 16 previous meta-analyses which covered 1798 studies (please see table 1). This large scale of studies provides strong evidences about 23 significant factors of gender differences from marketing perspective. These group of studies were selected among 70 meta-analyses after careful achieving of the research criteria. The large variety number of previous meta-analysis studies cannot be taken only for marketing segmentation, but also, to confirm the requirement of pink marketing term. The factors cover the dealing between females and males from the perspective of each one of them, that refers to marketing to/by women. Results show 9 factors favored females, as follows: using prefrontal regions of brain map working memory, more feel of shame and guilt, advantage in school marks, using of tentative language, learning orientation: reproduction, moral ethics/sensitivity and field studies. From another side, results refer to 12 factors favored males, as follows: using parietal regions of brain

map working memory, intelligence tests: general/mathematical-logical, spatial/verbal abilities, attitude toward cheating in school, involved in cyberbullying preparation, more feel of pride, favored as teachers from students, learning orientation: non-academic, self-esteem, personal self, athletic, physical appearance, self-satisfaction, academic self-efficacy: mathematics, computer and social sciences, gifted programs, job performance and outcome of negotiation. The other 2 factors refer to significant gender differences in allocation of brain map and three main functions of brain, that indicate both females and males use different ways in thinking and solving complex problems. The results indicate a set of important results. First, while females are psychological/ethical/sensitivity oriented, males are performance oriented. Second, the meta-analysis of [80] which included 209 of other previous studies favored males in Intelligence tests: general/mathematical-logical, spatial/verbal abilities.

Table 1
Study 1: Previous Meta-analysis Studies about Gender Differences

References	Studies	Gender Differences confirmed by results	More	
			F	M
[32]	59	Using prefrontal regions of Brain Map Working Memory	*	
		Using parietal regions of Brain Map Working Memory		*
		Indicates that men and women may use different strategies to solve complex problems		
[1]	70	Different allocation of brain during 3 main functions: visual-spatial/cognition/memory and emotion		
[80]	209	Intelligence tests: general/mathematical-logical, spatial/verbal abilities		*
[84]	48	Attitude toward cheating in school		*
[77]	39	Involved in cyberbullying preparation		*
[21]	382	More feel of shame and guilt	*	
		More feel of pride		*
[43]	38	Favored as teachers from students		*
[83]	369	Advantage in school marks	*	
[90]	29	Using of tentative language	*	
[70]	22	learning orientation: reproduction	*	
		learning orientation: non-academic		*
[25]	115	Self-esteem, personal self, athletic, physical appearance, self-satisfaction		*
		Moral ethics	*	
[89]	19	Moral sensitivity	*	
[33]	187	Academic self-efficacy: language art	*	
		Academic self-efficacy: mathematics, computer and social sciences		*
[62]	130	Gifted programs		*
[67]	61	Field studies	*	
		Job performance		*
[76]	21	Outcome of negotiation		*
16 Meta-analysis included 1798 Studies		23 factors of gender differences		

More Sig.= More Significant, F= Female, M= Male and *= Significant on the significance level 0.001.

4.3. Results of Study 2

Study 2 presents additional meta-analysis. It does not focus on specific factors of gender differences like most of other previous meta-analysis. Study 2 included a comprehensive survey and analyze 65 studies which covered 51 significant factors of gender differences for participations from more than 58 countries. Table 2 shows these significant factors of gender differences from the marketing perspective as well as what were presented in table 1. In other words, study 2 add more evidences to the results of study 1, with referring to the countries. These results confirm the inability of consolidated marketing, which not care about women characteristics. Results of 65 studies indicate to 30 factors favored females. The thirty factors may be grouped in four main categories, as follows: the way of using extra time in volunteering or to increase quality, the moral and ethical oriented, the attitude to online work in general and the focusing on relation/satisfaction/ loyalty. From another side, 21 factors favored males. These

factors may be categorized in four main groups, as follows: care about competition and insurance, performance oriented, high pricing and risk taking in decision/entrepreneurship/invest.

4.4. Groups of Gender Differences

Present meta-analysis included 81 of previous studies, which covered the results of 1863 studies. All these studies included the phrase Gender Differences in their titles. Moreover, these studies confirmed lot of gender differences from the marketing perspective, as follows:

4.4.1 Brain Working and Functions:

Around 59 studies confirmed that; while women use prefrontal regions of brain map working memory, men use parietal regions, that may be indication of using different strategies to solve problems [32]. Different allocation of brain during three main functions: visual-spatial/cognition/memory, were resulted by 70

studies [1]. Around 209 of previous studies favored men in the intelligence tests of general/mathematical-logical, spatial/verbal abilities [80].

4.4.2 Decisions of Risk Taking:

Females and males are different significantly in their decisions of risk taking [39], [5], [41], [71], [20]. They are different in their trust others [18]. However, these differences influence their way of dealing generally. Previous studies favored male in trust others and risk taking.

4.4.3. Online Transactions:

Previous studies favored women in online transactions, which included online shopping [46], buying [69], [45] and activities on social network sites [47]. Even, Neuro-marketing studies resulted different brain signals toward online work [65].

4.4.4. Negotiation and Offering:

[76] presented the results of 21 studies favored men in negotiation outcomes. While women focus on satisfaction and good relations, men focus on higher pricing [34]. Women present higher offers in contracting in general [12]. Solnick, (2001) indicated that women and men present higher offer to each other than their offers to the same gender.

4.4.5. Desire of Competition:

Previous studies favored men in the desire of competition generally [78], [59], [79], [26], [85].

4.4.6. Moral Decisions and Ethics:

Literature review indicated that women are more committed by ethics and moral decisions than men [7], [57], [48]. [77] discussed the results of 39 studies and favored men in cyberbullying preparation. In 1999 the study of [84] presented the results of 48 studies favored men in cheating.

4.4.7. Quality/Quantity Orientation:

While women are quality-oriented [54], [72], men are quantity-oriented [72]. A lot of previous studies favored men in care about increasing outcomes, profit and productivity [51], [37].

4.4.8. Shopping Behavior:

Women spend time on shopping more than men [11]. The most shopping motivations for women: fashion, adventure and value; for men: cost saving and convenience. Moreover, women are more care about brand loyalty [68], while men are more care about brand evaluation [10].

4.4.9. National/Universal Attitude:

Previous studies confirmed that women are impacted by national culture, while men are impacted by universal culture [36], [2], [7], [22]. Moreover, women are more effected by social influences [35], [29].

4.4.10. Volunteering and Relations Orientation:

A lot of previous studies favored women in care volunteering and relations [4], [51], [34], [61], [73].

4.4.11. Buy Decision of modern Technology:

Women are more optimistic in their buy decisions of new mobile devices and modern technology than men (Liu and Guo, 2017; Kotze et al., 2016; [27]; [58]).

4.4.12. Advertisement and Insurance:

Previous studies favored men in care about insurance [3], [49], [75]. moreover, men are more impacted by sexual words in advertisements than women [42]. [27] resulted that, women are more care about the right side of online advertisements, while men are more care about the left side.

4.5. Result of Hypothesis Test

All the results support the single research hypothesis. The study confirmed that significant gender differences require a specific term covering the marketing to/by women. According to the large scale of this meta-analysis, Pink Marketing is the suitable term to describe the marketing to/by women.

Table 2
Study 2: Meta-analysis Covers Previous Related Studies about Gender differences

References	Gender Differences confirmed by results	Countries	More Sig.	
			F	M
[4]	Volunteering and unpaid work	USA	*	
[91]		EU	*	
[61]		Netherlands	*	
[72]	Spend extra time to increase quality	General	*	
	Spend extra time to increase quantity			*
[78]	Desire of Competition	Austria		*
[59]		Japan		*
[79]		Austria		*
[26]		USA		*
[85]		General		*
[3]		Care about insurance	EU	
[49]	Italia			*
[75]	General			*
[39]	Risk taking in decisions/entrepreneurship/invest	Zimbabwe		*
[5]		Germany		*
[41]		Malaysia		*
[71]		General		*
[92]		General		*
[93]		USA		*
[18]	Trust others	Germany		*
[24]	Get more education	USA	*	
[17]		Indonesia	*	
[8]	Get more language acquisition	Canada	*	
[11]	Shopping time	Taiwan	*	
[93]		India	*	
[2]	Migration	USA	*	
[22]		UK	*	
[10]	Brand evaluation	USA		*
[68]	Brand loyalty	USA	*	
[94]	Optimistic with buy decision of mobile devices	Asia	*	
[95]	Optimistic with buy decision of high technologies	South Africa	*	
[27]	Preferences of mobile banking	Malaysia	*	
[58]		General	*	
[57]	More ethical decisions about marketing mix	UK	*	
[48]		USA	*	
([7])	More care about ethical decisions	Germany/ Italia/Japan	*	
	More Impacted by national culture		*	
	More Impacted by universal culture			*
[13]	Higher job expectations	China	*	
[40]	Higher job satisfaction	EU		*
[96]	Life satisfaction	General		*
[36]	Optimism in regarding abroad range of issues	18 countries		*
[47]	Commercial experiments on social Networks Sites	China	*	
[14]		General	*	
[46]	More online shopping/buy	General	*	
[69]		USA	*	
[45]		Canada	*	
[65]		General	*	
[28]	Brain activity toward online work	General	*	
	More Care about the right side of online advertise	USA	*	

	More Care about the left side of online advertise			*
[99]	Shopping motivations for fashion/adventure/value	Taiwan	*	
	Shopping motivations for cost saving/convenience			*
[35]	Positive effect by Social influences	South Korea	*	
[97]		Australia	*	
[29]		General	*	
[42]	more impacted by sexual words in advertisement	Australia/New Zealand		*
[51]	Focus on emotions and interaction	Australia	*	
	Focus on outcome-oriented and functional			*
[37]	More care about profit maximize	General		*
[98]	More care about increase of productivity	General		*
[60]	Preference more interventionism by government	Poland	*	
[63]	Competitiveness in politics	USA		*
[44]	Higher in Equity sensitivity	General	*	
[73]	Customer oriented	General	*	
[54]	Quality oriented	UK	*	
[52]	Decision to Coauthor in research publish	General	*	
[53]	More quality and quantity of researches	USA		*
[12]	Give higher offer in contracting	General	*	
[74]	Give higher offer for women in contracting	General		*
	Give higher offer for men in contracting		*	
[16]	Higher performance in selling of stock	General		*
	Give higher prices in selling of stock		*	
[34]	More Focus on Prices in selling	General		*
	More focus on satisfaction and good relations		*	
65 Studies	51 factors of gender differences	More than 58 Countries		

More Sig.= More Significant, F= Female, M= Male and *= Significant on the significance level 0.001.

5. CONCLUSION

This section discusses how the study achieved its objectives and summarize the added value to the literature. Conclusion part included five sub-sections; overall conclusion, pink marketing framework, cautions for interpretation, study contributions and suggested future research.

5.1. Overall Conclusion

Present study aimed to investigate how the marketing literature is in need to confirm the pink marketing concept? Three strategies were used to achieve this main objective. First strategy, wide search about the using the term of Pink Marketing among more than 77 million references on 7 large sources included in WOS database (from 1900-May2017). The results confirm that no reference used this concept clearly in all of these references, it was only used under the title Marketing to Women. Second strategy, study 1 analyzed 16 of previous meta-analysis studies which covered 1798 studies with presenting a large set of evidences about significance of gender differences. Third

strategy, study 2 referred to the results of 65 studies applied on more than 58 countries and confirmed the significance of gender differences. Both study 1 and 2 searched WOSCC database (from 1900-May2017), which included more than 64 million references through large six cited indexes. Present study supported more than significant 74 factors of gender differences from the marketing perspective. 39 factors favored females, while 33 factors favored males and two factors indicated to the significant differences of thinking and solving problems. Therefore, these results included a lot of various and variety gender differences. The results of present study are consistent with the results of all previous studies which were included by the research criteria. Current study suggested strongly to adopt the term of Pink Marketing. Furthermore, study presented a necessary support for academics and practitioners to better understanding of gender differences.

5.2. Pink Marketing Framework

All the presented results help in proposing a primary framework for pink marketing. This

framework includes three main groups of items. First group for Marketing by Women (or Woman as a Marketer). This group includes 9 main factors favored women, as follows: giving higher prices, presenting higher offers through negotiation, customer-oriented, relations-oriented, ethics and moral decision, quality-oriented, immigration, higher attitude to online working and transactions and high care about volunteering. Second group for Marketing to Women (or Woman as a Customer). This group includes 9 main factors favored women, as follows: ethics and moral decisions, online transactions, product loyalty, care about product evaluation, shopping, modern devices, education, tentative language and care about the important of the right side of advertisement page. Third group includes 9 main not-favored women, as follows: risk taking, satisfaction in general, competitiveness, quantitative-oriented performance, care about insurance and warranty, speed of decision taking, feeling of pride, selling outcomes and intelligence tests of general/mathematical-logical/spatial/verbal abilities.

5.3. Cautions for Interpretation

The cautions for interpretation; there are three main limitations in this study. First caution, only the English language was confirmed in this study. Second caution, although, the large capacity of *WOSCC*, but study depended on this database only. Third caution, criteria included specific phrases in the survey, as detailed before, especially "Gender Differences". Moreover, author depended on all these ways to avoid the bias in interpretation and resulting.

5.4. Study Contributions

This study aimed to answer four main questions and test just one research hypothesis, about the term of Pink Marketing. The four questions were answered through the study with explanations and details, the hypothesis was tested and supported. The results of this study came compatible with the previous studies about confirming the gender differences, especially from the modern marketing perspective. The results of 1863 previous studies were collected in this present meta-analysis covered more than 74 factors of gender differences from marketing perspective. The essential added value of this study is the highlighting the marketing to/by women, and the need of the term Pink Marketing in the marketing literature. These results confirm the inability of the consolidated marketing strategy.

5.5. Suggested Future Research

Future researchers may maximize the contributions of this study by more effort to create an integrated framework of pink marketing. Furthermore, academics should to give more attention about presenting meta-analysis studies to enrich the marketing thought on the context of theoretical building.

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